

Spectroscopic and conductivity studies on pyridazine metal complexes

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Complexes of types $[ML_2(H_2O)_2]Cl_2$ and $[ML_2(H_2O)_2]Cl_3$, where L is *N*-phenyl-3-carboethoxy-4-methyl-5-cyanopyridazin-6-one (PCMC) and M = Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}, have been prepared. The complexes are octahedrally coordinated. Crystal field parameters $10 Dq$ and B have been calculated. Electrical conductivity data show that these complexes behave like typical organic semiconductors. A correlation between activation energy and ionic radius is given.

Diazines and pyridazines exhibit various biological activities^{1,2}. The vibrational spectra of diazine-metal complexes have elicited some attention. Child *et al.*¹ studied some diazine transition metal complexes in the IR region.

The present work was undertaken in an attempt to synthesize some metal chelates of pyridazine and characterize them using spectroscopic techniques and magnetic susceptibility measurements. Also, the electrical conductivity of these complexes has been measured.

Results and Discussion

The isolated complexes were formulated either as $[ML_2(H_2O)_2]Cl_2$ (M = Mn, Co, Ni or Cu having yellowish buff, dark brown, pale green and pale blue colour, respectively) or, $[ML_2(H_2O)_2]Cl_3$ [M = Cr or Fe exhibiting yellowish green and brown colour, respectively).

IR spectra : The ligand showed two IR peaks at 2214 (C≡N) and 1630 cm⁻¹ (C=O). Upon complexation, these bands shifted to lower frequencies suggesting that the ligand is coordinated to the metal ions via the carbonyl oxygen and nitrogen atom of the cyano group. The presence of coordinated water molecules³ is confirmed by the appearance of two peaks at 3340 and 760 cm⁻¹.

Electronic spectra : The electronic spectral parameters for complexes are calculated⁴. No absorption peaks were observed for the ligand in the studied region. The appearance of new bands for metal chelates is attributed to complex formation. Three absorption features were observed for the Co^{II} chelate at 6800, 13550 and 17150 cm⁻¹ attributed to ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 transitions, respectively. The presence of these features indicates that Co^{II} ion has an octahedral environment⁴. Two peaks were observed for the Ni^{II} chelate at 11778 and 20430 cm⁻¹, attributed to ν_2 and ν_3 , respectively. Also, two bands observed at 14225 and 18700 cm⁻¹ for the Cr^{III} complex could be attributed to ν_1 and ν_2 , respectively. The values of ($10 Dq$ and B) as calculated for the Co, Ni and Cr complexes are (8500, 803), (6450, 839)

and (13564, 897) cm⁻¹, respectively. The observed peak in the spectrum of the Cu^{II} chelate is attributed to Jahn-Teller effect⁴. The reduction in B values for all the complexes as compared with the free-ion values reveals the complex formation⁴. The electronic spectral bands and their $10 Dq$ values indicate that all the complexes are octahedrally coordinated.

Magnetic susceptibility : The magnetic moment values indicate that the complexes are of high-spin configuration with octahedral geometry. The Co^{II} chelate ($\mu_{eff} = 4.77$

Fig. 1. Variation of electrical conductivity as a function of reciprocal of absolute temperature for ligand and metal chelates.

Table 1. Values of activation energy (E_1 , E_2), electrical conductivity (σ_l , σ_{II}) and transition temperature (T_c) for the ligand and metal complexes*

Compd.	T_c K	E_1 eV	E_2 eV	$\sigma_l \times 10^{-6}$ $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 333 K	$\sigma_{II} \times 10^{-5}$ $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 434 K	Ionic radius Å
Ligand	384	0.06	0.75	0.355	0.614	–
Mn complex	399	0.14	0.63	2.376	2.347	0.80
Fe complex	385	0.09	0.32	4.552	2.040	0.64
Cr complex	392	0.16	0.41	0.966	0.750	0.69
Co complex	401	0.10	0.53	13.674	8.272	0.74
Ni complex	386	0.28	0.48	0.791	1.511	0.72
Cu complex	395	0.18	0.49	10.544	10.103	0.72

* E_1 = Activation energy in the lower temperature range, E_2 = activation energy in the higher temperature range, σ_l = electrical conductivity measured at lower temperature, σ_{II} = electrical conductivity measured at higher temperature.

B.M.) exhibits appreciable spin-orbit coupling contribution. On the contrary, no spin-orbit coupling contribution was observed in case of the Ni^{II} and Cr^{III} chelates ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 3.25$ and 3.89 B.M., respectively). This agrees with the crystal field theory predictions⁵.

All the complexes reacted with AgNO₃ in aqueous ethanol forming a white quantitative precipitate of AgCl, which indicates the cationic nature of the complexes.

Electrical conductivity : The temperature-dependence of electrical conductivity is shown in Fig. 1. It reveals a linear trend with break suggesting phase transition⁶⁻⁹ of two systems distinguished by different activation energies. The values of activation energy and conductivity are listed in Table 1. All samples behave as organic semiconductors^{7,8}. It is clear that the delocalized *d*-orbital electrons contribute as charge carrier. The conductivity shows a tendency to increase by rising temperature. The lower temperature range is the region of extrinsic semiconductor where conduction is attributed to the excitation of carriers from donor localized levels to the conduction band. The higher temperature range is the region of intrinsic semiconductor, where carriers are thermally activated from valence band to conduction band. It is clear that transition metal ion has a considerable effect on the value of activation energy E_2 . The E_2 is linearly dependent on the ionic radius¹⁰ of the metal ions as illustrated in Table 1.

Experimental

The ligand *N*-phenyl-3-carboethoxy-4-methyl-5-cyanopyridazin-6-one (PCMC), m.p. 149 ± 1°, was prepared as reported earlier¹¹. Metal chelates were prepared by refluxing aqueous ethanolic solutions of the ligand and the metal chlorides of Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} in the appropriate ratio 2 : 1 (ligand : metal) for 1 h and then cooled. The resulting metal chelates were washed with ethanol and ether, and dried under reduced pressure (yields ~78%).

Electronic spectra (DMF) were recorded on Prekin-Elmer

λ3b and Carl-Zises PMQII spectrophotometers and IR spectra (KBr) on a Shimadzu IR 440 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature using the Gouy method, and the effective magnetic moments μ_{eff} were calculated⁵. Electrical conductivity (d.c.) was measured at different temperatures from room temperature up to near the melting point of each sample using the potential probe method^{6,7}.

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